

CULTURES OF FAIR AND DECENT WORK

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Fair and Decent Work

Fair and decent work is a profound global challenge, often discussed with respect to themes and factors concerning pay and poverty, employment status and precariousness, work-life balance impacting adversely on family and wellbeing problems related to stress. For SME employers who are good fair and decent work employers, business champions, we wondered if there might be lessons that could be learned and shared about their cultures and behaviours, which might help and guide others. This report is the outcome of a study inspired by that.

It is widely accepted that many factors are in play shaping the future of work, including the growth of the 'gig' economy, automation, changing generational expectations of work and careers, and enlightened attitudes to mental health. For these to work through positively will require many more SMES to appreciate and pay attention to the factors identified here in the lessons from business champions.

Our approach to research with impact is based on systemic culture change Organization Development (OD), and developing resources for employers to access and use. This means we seek to collect and feedback data in collaboration with employers to learn from a range of voices and identify the best interventions for change. Culture analysis and OD methods are concerned with positively promoting change by discovering, imagining, and delivering inspiring voices and stories.

For more information on this

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Introduction

This study identifies aspects of PROUD fair and decent work cultures identified in Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) organizations who are fair and decent work employers, business champions of this. These relate to the culture and behaviour themes of;

- Purpose; Responsible Leads, Values
- Results; Resourceful
- Open Communication; Clan culture, Kindness
- Unified; One Team
- Differences; Quick Learning

These PROUD cultures emerge from studying fair and decent work explicitly and directly in the SME sector. The sample includes SME organizations in both manufacturing and service sectors.

Seven SME organizations who were perceived to fulfil the characteristics of a fair and decent work. There were interviews with directors or senior managers. A survey was distributed to employees, with 78 respondents from these 7 organizations. An overview of the benchmark data from the study and in each is given in the report by;

- Core score perceptions of fair and decent work
- Benchmark data on 6 factors
- Organization Profiles

Employee Survey respondents in these cases were asked if their current employer was the best they had worked for; 55% said yes, they were. Another 26% rated them as similar to other employers experienced. Only 14% said they were not the best, and 5% could not compare. We believe this validates the sample of cases here a being a sample of fair and decent work employer.

Our main recommendations are;

1. Advocates of fair and decent work understand the lessons and promote awareness of these as OD pathways to progress with SME employers who are more ambivalent or need to be persuaded about the advantages of being FDW employers.
2. Organizations can self-assess specifically around the themes here, and with dialogue and stakeholder engagement develop their organizations.
3. To facilitate a community of learning about these lessons training and workshops targeted at SMEs should be provided.

This report may be freely shared and distributed as long as full acknowledgement of the origin of the resource and author is respected and clearly given.

Gibb, S. (2019) **Fair and Decent Work in Scotland; The Seven Capabilities of Successful SME Organizations**, University of West of Scotland.

Context and Method

The organizations included in this study were identified in a single and discrete local socio-economic area, from organizations with existing connections to UWS who were believed to be potential business champions of Fair and Decent Work (FDW).

No of Employees per organization	No in survey	% of workforce
12	10	83%
19	11	58%
93	24	26%
29	7	24%
17	4	24%
46	7	15%
108	14	13%

The overall mean from all survey respondents about their perceptions of their current employer as providing decent work is 4.3 with a maximum of 5. This indicates a strong and positive evaluation of the employers who participated in the study, as a sample of decent work employers. Table 1 shows the means for all 6 factors associated with FDW, for the sample as a whole and then for each organization.

Table 1; All Study Factor Means							
		Pay	Well	Ctrl	Terms	Supt	Sat
All	4.3	3.8	4.0	3.9	4.1	4.0	4.1
O1	4.1	4.4	4.3	4.3	4.5	4.4	4.5
O2	3.9	3.5	3.5	3.1	3.7	3.2	3.9
O3	3.8	2.9	3.9	3.3	3.3	4.0	3.3
O4	5.0	4.8	4.9	4.9	4.9	5.0	4.9
O5	4.7	4.3	4.7	4.3	4.6	5.0	4.9
O6	4.4	3.2	4.0	3.8	4.0	4.2	4.0
O7	4.1	3.6	3.8	3.9	4.0	3.8	3.9

The overall employee estimation of decent work ranges from a maximum of 5 to the lowest of 3.8. The mean is 4.3.

The means for the 6 factors which were identified as the systemic foundations of decent work are, in order;

- **Satisfaction** 4.1
- **Terms of employment** 4.1
- **Wellbeing** 4.0
- **Support** 4.0
- **Control** 3.9
- **Pay** 3.8

These validate the sample being FDW employers and business champions in this area. Evidently when individual factors are considered the perception of these is typically less positive than the overall rating of decent work as a whole. This is evidence that even among the best there are factors ‘interfering’ with the achievement of fair and decent work.

The profiles of the seven organizations across all 6 factors is shown below. The profile of each organization is broadly similar, with each factor weighted more or less equally.

For those organizations where the ratings are most high (Organization 4 and Organization 5) they approach the maximum score possible, 30.

Where ratings are lowest, in organization 2 and organization 3, these are still scoring at least 20 out of 30.

Concerns

A question about potential concerns was included in the data collection, for triangulation and cross checking. These identified job security, training, career development, control at work and recognition.

From most to least concern (1 = No Concern, 3 = Very Concerned) the ratings were as follows;

- **Recognition** 1.5
- **Career** 1.4
- **Training** 1.3
- **Control** 1.3
- **Security** 1.2

The findings on concerns do triangulate well with the sample being fair and decent employers. It is noticeable, for example, that some respondents who have provided very positive evaluations of their employer as a whole indicate being ‘very concerned’ about some things.

The concerns can be further explored in various ways to identify themes and also groups (by age, gender, role) where further consideration may be helpful and actionable.

The most common profile on concerns is no concern about any factors (38%); then next having concerns with one or two things (35%). Of the remaining 25 respondents only, a few had more than three concerns.

There is no single concern which emerges distinctly in each organization or the overall study.

Conclusions

This sample of organizations provides a pool to help ground and establish lessons for FDW in SMES. These lessons can be used by other SMEs to self-evaluate where they stand, and either celebrate that success or identify issues and concerns that could be addressed to change.

Systemic OD is needed to advance FDW and can be enabled by other SMEs collecting data and benchmarking, to identify areas where interventions might be possible and make a positive difference. The audiences for these can be segmented and described as ‘ambivalent employers and ‘persuadable employers’

Culture Case Lessons	PROUD Ongoing Challenges & Issues	Culture Change Themes	Culture Change Actions
S& C Engineering One Team	Pay and satisfaction appear to be issues, along with concerns about careers	Directors need to be familiar with coaching, so a coaching model as a way forward might be appropriate	Being 'one team', needs to be led and shared by others in management roles, not by HR
XS Stock Resourceful	An issue with pay being identified, along with a concern in the area of careers.	Extending being efficient for the type of company they are. They don't use anyone from outside if they don't need to.	They operate 'tight', everyone has a key role and is required; HR multi-tasking beyond professional boundaries
Worksmart Clan Culture	Ratings are among the highest in the study in a whole but overall employee evaluation is below the average.	Leaders to Build and maintain such a culture to reduce high turnover in some roles.	HR can intervene explicitly to build and maintain such a culture to reduce high turnover in some roles
M& M Theatre Kindness	The ratings on the 6 factors are among the lowest. With concerns among the highest with recognition and control.	The workforce, and the logistical reality of the operations, requiring a substantial degree of care and effort on the part of many people.	What HR policy and practices can support this? Is HR the role model for this?
KCP Waste Management Values	No single factor stands out, the culture which has been established around values, the CHESS culture	Insights and commitments of owners are essential, while growth involves these adopting more 'hands off' roles.	Know and shape the challenges of the local labour market for the retention of operators and professional staff who might help with growth.
Thorne Travel; Responsible owner	Above average and the highest on all factors, with least concerns. Fit with the ethos and customer needs.	The personal focus of the director on knowing and meeting their own work-life needs and expecting to fulfil the same for others.	HR Support a dynamic, team spirit throughout.
Brodie Engineering; Quick Learning	3 years, to build trust and respect for the function of HR.	A strategic review led by leaders, giving 'recognition' and reward for this.	Set up formal values, asking the most of HR knowledge and expertise as a business partners.

Case and Company Reports

S& C Engineering; Executive Summary and Actions

Compared with the study as a whole the factors of pay and satisfaction appear to be issues, along with concerns about careers. In terms of expressing concerns these are all slightly higher in S&C than in the sample as a whole.

This suggests that while these achievements are positive there is scope to do more in all areas. The directors are familiar with coaching, so a coaching model which identified decent work goals, checked realities, considered options and a way forward might be appropriate.

In adopting that coaching style of inquiry prior to action it might be possible to call on external support, though the process is best owned and managed by the directors.

The dynamic and innovative approach seen to rebranding and in the 'meet the team' video can be harnessed perhaps in other areas too, the softer aspect of satisfaction and also the harder aspect of pay and total rewards.

Actions

The issues of pay and satisfaction, along with concerns about careers, can be further explored using a coaching style and process.

The growth and strategic success that has been achieved by how the directors work together in approachability, and to have good people working for them, as one team, might need to be shared by others

in management as growth is sustained or increased.

Organization Data

Table 1 (decent work factors) and Table 2 (Concerns with 3 = high concern, 1 = no concern) show the main findings from the survey, which 7 people completed. The overall rating of 3.8 as a decent work employer was the lowest in the study, though this is still a positive rating. It can be seen that compared with the study as a whole the issues of pay and satisfaction appear to be the areas underpinning these results, along with concerns about careers. In terms of expressing concerns these are all slightly higher in S&C than in the sample as a whole.

Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		
	All	Your Organization
Overall employee evaluation	4.3	3.8
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	3.3
Terms of employment	4.1	3.3
Wellbeing	4.0	4.0
Support	4.0	3.9
Control	3.9	3.3
Pay	3.8	2.9

Concerns (3 = high concern, 1 = no concern)		
	All	Your Organization
Recognition	1.5	1.7
Career	1.4	1.9
Training	1.3	1.6
Control	1.3	1.4

Security	1.2	1.3
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S&C Engineering Significant themes

The current owners had very clear vision when started. They are getting there heading in the right direction.

The big thing is they did not come into this as professionals, so every day is a learning curve for them.

They now have a team where the job really does matter. They are very competitive with Glasgow markets that pay a bit more, people coming to them not for more money but a better work life.

They tend to look at employees reward personally, not as a whole.

They do employ an HR company that they can go to if they have any employment issues, they can't deal with it themselves.

Decent Work Factors

Pay

They have not experienced challenges with living wage, they do it anyway. Not a lot of demands from any sector on employee benefits or processes and procedures, no questions on those.

Tend to look at employees personally, not as a whole, performance and effort and going beyond and award individually reward and encourage. Financially with vouchers, charitable, a personal point of view, what would that person like to be recognized.

Satisfaction

They don't have a great turnover, so they take that as a good sign. They had an OD review and survey of everyone, and it was good when it came back, comments from employees, people love being part of a family business, colleagues, and variety of work.

Terms of employment

All on permanent contracts. They sometimes employ agency workers, mostly when they take them on after 12 weeks. After for 12 weeks if they like it and the owners like them, they become permanent.

Wellbeing

They have a compliance manager doing a lot of work on H&S in the workshop; monitoring sound levels, vibration, fumes, extraction. The facilities have been upgraded, lovely canteen and toilet facilities. Putting a radio in for them was the big ask, once the one person who did not want it retired, so they have that now. They feel on the ball when it comes to keeping employees happy.

Support

East Ayrshire provided coaching and management coaching courses; they always emphasise it is a part of continuous improvement. 4 of the management team are coming towards the end of their career, and they have one Graduate Apprentice (GA) in their 20s. Managers can be reluctant to delegate so they do a lot of work as a team and the

things people can bring to that team, understand what is available to them.

Control/Voice

Suggestion boxes in the canteen, if implemented get meal vouchers. Toolbox talks are used, staff put the tools down gather round and have a conversation and an opportunity to ask questions, keep up to date.

The big thing for the owners is they did not come into this as professionals, so every day is a learning curve for them so they have to listen to other people and when you are in the mix and you are pushing on there are things you done notice that others can bring to your attention, so you need to be approachable

Context

The company was established in 1947, one co-owner/director served his apprenticeship here. He bought the company when the owner retired 12 years ago, it was archaic, they wanted to change the image. A whole new brand, new colours and logos and name, to get away from the historical agricultural engineer that the business had been. Their markets are changing all the time, with the rise and fall of different sectors, they wanted to expand into different sectors. Their team ethos was a big part of that so the transition that has taken part has involved the team around them.

They look for the potential to grow, never ready-made they have to look for the potential to develop them into the engineer they are looking for. Most advertising is through social media and

word of mouth. Employees like the variety of work and come to work and do something different every day, and expand their skill base, that's a big thing for them, they get a lot CVS and enquiries.

There are 29 employees; 6 production side office based, 2 finance, workshop apprentice, semi-skilled, engineer and senior engineers. HR stuff done by her, one of the many hats

The owners and managers are a wife and husband, equal partners. The husband worked for two other companies; other family-owned SMEs then came back to S&C Engineering.

Culture

Their meet the team video is very popular and different. It's difficult to get a website that isn't over complicated and too diverse to understand S&C as a business and contact, buy into S&C as a business and pick up the phone. The video was to show S&C are approachable, have good people working for them, they are one team and it's a fun time, employees really like to be here, and like what they do and what they do for customers. They all see each other as one team. Their customers feel part of that too. They have had brilliant feedback, not just a boring engineering video, selling S&C as a company.

Business and Management Development

They have not got accreditation specific to employment, they have ISO, safe contractor status, and did actually get 'IIP young people' as an award. But when it came to renew it and had not heard from them for three years. They are not sure

what they got from the award, though it would cost around £600 for it and could not justify that when they did not know what they are getting. nothing to warrant them putting out that sort of money.

They get great support from the LA, helping to grow the business, and stay in the locality also for that reason too.

The local Labour market is very challenging, because they are a bespoke engineering company every day is different, every customer is different, every job is different, they need people to be highly skilled and not people who are used to standing at a machine and doing the same thing every day.

Probably one of the biggest challenges they had was when the oil and gas market slipped away, then they were getting a lot of CVs from engineers. However, these people were looking for a lot of money but not the skills to match. If they took them on and invested in them as soon as an option came up, they would leave for the money in other sectors, so making this all a waste of investment.

Only certain people, of the right mindset, are going to fit; it's not just the money, they now have a team where the job really does matter. They are very competitive compared with larger city labour markets nearby that pay a bit more, coming to S&C for money and a better work life.

Farming is more self-sustaining, but farming is not what it used to be. Now there are so many other industries better for them. The big one for them is the rail sector, companies looking for engineering support, food and drink, Local Authorities and health boards, and defence including the MOD, the aircraft side of things. Lot of

different sectors now, they found out very quickly if they had a lot of construction work then that collapsed there was a big impact of collapse, so aim for more of a spread and balance.

They employ an HR company that they can go to if needed (a specialist, Citation HR). If they have any issues, they seek to deal with these themselves, they had for example a meeting on two employees to be disciplined, ticking all the boxes they should, the HR support can guide them.

Personal

They keep their social media pages up to date, what they are doing with employees, with apprentices, with schools Strathclyde University link and motor sport. Facebook, twitter, linked in.

While markets are changing, they like where they are, they like being part of a community, the transport links are very good.

XS Stock; Executive Summary and Actions

The overall evaluation of decent work is 4.4., though in the constituent factors there is an issue with pay being identified, along with a concern in the area of careers.

- Focus on the factor of pay
- Explore what the career concern means.

Organization Data

Table 1 and 2 show the main findings from the survey, which 5 people completed. The overall evaluation of decent work is 4.4., though in the constituent factors there is an issue with pay being identified, along with a concern in the area of careers.

Variables of Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		
	All	Your Organization
Overall employee evaluation	4.3	4.4
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	4.0
Terms of employment	4.1	4.0
Wellbeing	4.0	4.2
Support	4.0	4.0
Control	3.9	3.8
Pay	3.8	3.2

Concerns	All	Your Organization
Recognition	1.5	1.4
Career	1.4	2.0
Training	1.3	1.2
Control	1.3	1.0
Security	1.2	1.0

XS Stock; Significant themes

XS Stock started in 1994, owned by Adrian Hodge as MD. Trade type warehousing, and the e-commerce aspect to the company has grown considerable. Now they get 99.7 positive feedback, after 13 years of trading. XS Stock get first option for opportunities, and calls to do new things, given their reputation and record.

The sector is a 'beast' and a 'monster', it's not about simply building a web site. Courses on web design are what many offers that, but they need to teach you about budgets, employment, and the rest.

Work and Employment

Pay

They are working towards the living wage and do pay above minimum wage but not to the accreditation level of the living wage.

Satisfaction

There is a mixed view on this. Some of the work is mundane and can be done on autopilot. Everyone does a good job, some do better.

Satisfaction is built around the social make-up of the office and warehouse. If you have a bad apple you have an issue. Presently staff get on well, sometimes too well, and need to be reminded 'shut up and get on with it'!

Terms of employment

There are no zero hours contracts. XS Stock are against them morally and operationally. They do not bring people in at 3 in the morning to wait for work. They specify if a job is for x hours and provide an induction process and offer to increase hours if it gets busier. They have had ex Amazon staff and the feedback from them is quite scary, it is hard to believe they (Amazon) can get away with what they do.

The local Labour market is good, and they feel very fortunate with the staff brought in, from a massive labour market out there. What they have found is they get approached twice a month by recruitment agencies but tend not to use them. They recruit directly from Facebook and mailing list, mainly local people. They put an ad out, for one position, for additional packers on a Monday for an 8-hour shift. They had 437 applicants for a one-day shift. They work trials and use that rather than sit down in an interview, what's required in the position, do 4-hour shift, and get paid for that.

Wellbeing

Some staff bring in expertise from work with consultants on H&S and employment law, and they have also identified a person to be hired for risk assessments, toolbox talks and assessments. As they get bigger, they need specific advice.

Warehousing context and team's safety is key. There is an appreciation that a safety

culture takes time to build, they are a year away from 100%. But from zero to hero takes 7 years.

Support

Last year they worked with 'Working Links', a government organised employment support project, in a phased approach up to Xmas, based on having a high staff need for 'Black Friday'. They somehow got an older workforce, which changed the whole balance of the workforce, a positive change. Less problems, less timekeeping issues, less 'messing around'. This was not planned for but worked for them. If you get the balance right it is so much easier, and that can be difficult, as managers start of managing staff and end up managing personalities, individuals not groups. Last year worked well and all were invited back, which was unheard of in past years.

Control/Voice

Management in SME is more human and personal than central rules and systems. They are very efficient for the type of company they are. The software sold to make them more efficient, showed them that what they were already doing was as fast. They learned about smart picking and that has brought benefit. It is possible to be efficient and run effectively without losing the personal approach

As they grew bigger and needed a strong foundation and clear channels of communication, to get the right information and who to talk to. There is a structural level in the organisation; MD to manager to team leaders, and a person for customers service, another for warehouse, and one in finance. The manager cascades to them and they can pass it on. They have tried and failed to establish team

meetings, which work in the quiet period but not in peak sessions. In peak season it is all hands to pump, then hard to re-establish team meetings again.

Work and Employment

Their trade type is warehousing, with the e-commerce aspect to the company having grown considerably. Very early they realised potential also changed the way they were operating, and built-up own website, ebay presence, with multiple eBay shops. Now they get 99.7 positive feedback, after 13 years of trading.

The sector it is a beast and a monster, not about simply building a web site. Courses on web design are what many offers that, but they need to teach you about budgets, employment, and the rest.

They are two separate companies, XS stock.com limited, AHL group. Life is difficult but interesting.

Perceptions of XS as stocking seconds, 'end of lines', what people don't want. That's not what XS stock is, it is rather about seeing each week who has too much quality branded products, they want to shift it and see it sold on at reduced rates. That allowed customers to benefit, so they are of the Aldi or Lidl ilk. They do what they do and do it well.

XS Stock has 17 members of staff, increasing in peak season October to December to 35. Attrition rate is very low. There are 5 creatives, one management and the warehouse staff with 1 full time and 2 part time plus others at peak periods.

The company started in 1994, owned by Adrian Hodge as MD. The MD and his father, and wife runs the store with a

general manager in the store but not in XS Stock as being small they did not need that.

Culture

What they have tried to do, as they are control freaks, is they don't use anyone from outside if they don't need to. They look at skill sets in the staff and do training. Even so they don't do as much development as they would like to and want to do more management skills courses.

They do believe they are good at what they do. For companies in N Ayrshire, they can offer how to sell on-line, and part of their plan is open an e commerce academy,

Staff are not typical either; one not an on-line person by background but because she had the right attitude and hard worker. She has a degree in fine art, and has creative mind, that was a great starting point. She has also become a yoga instructor.

Business and Management Development

Many people want to do this kind of business but don't know where to start. They go on eBay, but that is harder than using your own website, and margins may go as they are not taking account their fees and PayPal fees, and carrier fees. Selling on e-commerce is easy as a hobby, but even just employ one person and the whole game changes.

XS reputation grew, and staffing increased, and from 2011 and they had to ramp up operations considerably. With orders from eBay, web and Amazon not just working dealing with a warehouse full of stock but a management system telling you where it

all is. Amazon and eBay selected them as a testing partner click and collect. They did the same with Prime, so they no longer have to send to a fulfilment centre, they send from direct from their site governed by rules for prime sellers. This allows sales to grow at least 30% because of a prime badge, 80% go to see what's on Prime; why pay for it if not getting it tomorrow?

On top of that they realised early on the need to identify the staff and bring them in. They used to have a room to take pictures and put up, but they brought in a lead for the creative department, videography photography writing and listing. A team of 5 that do all that now. They established the standard; they have their own photo studio. Feedback from customers is that this it makes it easier to engage and buy, and important for good customer service.

2014 was busiest year ever, it was chaos. A new warehouse management system was in place, as paper-based pick-pack was too slow and errors. They can measure and KPI all employees to see if they are efficient. They went into peak season with the new system not fully tested. That was stressful!

Personal

The manager and MD have known each other since they were children. The manager's path took him through leisure centres and performance management,

The manager himself previously managed various leisure centres, to identify under performers and was sent in to fix these. Now knows well how to manage staff fairly, with a strong working knowledge of

health and safety, and a believer in investing in staff. However, they operate tight, minimum number of staff, everyone has a key role and is required, so it is hard to get people on courses.

He enjoys sports karate, being a member in a group for that which operates out of a converted 'B listed' building. This building was offered funding from a railway heritage trust, but development ground to a halt. He stepped in to help. With his XS stock experience he helped with the creation of a business plan. They redid the funding application. That succeeded and indeed that plan is now seen as an industry standard business plan. A lot of people never write a business plan, they have it in the head or know but don't write it down.

Most of his qualifications are in leisure, but he has a passion about employment law, as it is often so badly managed and misunderstood. It's not just employees it's also employers, and how to use it fairly; some employees are so misinformed, they think they can get this, they can't. A reasonable employer would follow due process.

Conclusion

The overall evaluation of decent work is good though in the constituent factors there is an issue with pay being identified, along with a concern in the area of careers.

The company can explore the theme of pay and rewards.

The company can explore what the career concern means.

Worksmart; Executive Summary and Actions

As an award-winning business Worksmart appreciates their people. There has been growth, but the aim is to still be a family run company, a family focused company, a Worksmart family.

Managers appreciate that ‘you are never going to please everyone’ but would not expect anyone to say that even although there might be instances that things are not 100% for them that it’s not fair. That is entirely borne out and seen in the result of the 7 respondents to the survey. The decent work ratings are among the highest in the study in a whole, in most respects.

However, the overall employee evaluation for Worksmart, which they would expect to be higher than the average given the component factor scores, is below the average.

The idea of fulfilment is going to be different for different people and the recruitment and retention issues vary also. Challenges are evident in resourcing some skilled and professional staff, and to retain joiners. An ongoing issue is the location of work; sometimes it all based in Edinburgh, or Ayrshire or Aberdeen.

Actions

Reflect on why component factor scores which are higher than average is not reflected in an overall higher than average evaluation- perhaps there is a factor missing in what decent work means in Worksmart which this study is not identifying yet?

There is a challenge of building and maintaining teams where there is a high turnover in some roles, across those who are office based and those who are

As a brand aware organization perhaps one of the employment related accreditations would be a ‘stretch’ challenge for Worksmart to help bring together all staff to build on and complement the ‘values’ work which has been done.

WorkSmart Key Data

Table 1 (decent work factors) and Table 2 (Concerns with 3 = high concern, 1 = no concern) show the main findings from the survey. The scores on the 6 factors in table 1 are among the highest of all the study companies. And the lack of concerns seen in Table 2 are also among the lowest. What is interesting though, recognising these very strong results, is that the overall employee evaluation which they would expect to be higher than the average is below the average.

Variables of Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		
	All	Your Organization
Overall employee evaluation	4.3	4.0
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	4.9
Terms of employment	4.1	4.6
Wellbeing	4.0	5.0
Support	4.0	4.7
Control	3.9	4.3
Pay	3.8	4.3

Concerns	All	Your Organization
Recognition	1.5	1.0
Career	1.4	1.3
Training	1.3	1.1
Control	1.3	1.0
Security	1.2	1.0

Worksmart Significant Themes

Clients are very varied, they have worked with housing associations and councils and the Scottish government, and Police Scotland.

Keep it as a family run company, a family focused company

Being very logo orientated, branding matters a great deal.

The HR role is evolving supported by experience, knowledge and technology to provide an expert capacity, and as a business partner.

There is variety in the recruitment and retention challenge across roles

Decent Work Factors

Pay

They are very good payers, though they don't think money is the big issue locally. Reasons for people leaving are usually something else like the amount of travel involved.

They pay over and above the minimum wage, and always have done. Apprentices

are regulated (SBTC), regulated so they make sure they follow that.

I would say in rewards they as a company are very good at recognising, and above and beyond reward, beyond their role which they do at their company meetings and sometimes £50 of M&S vouchers.

Satisfaction

Everybody's idea of fulfilment is different so it's hard for any manager to say for sure. The joiners are fulfilled if they have done a perfect job, that's not others idea.

They encourage people to come and ask if they want to do something that will help their role, or qualification. The apprentices who became joiners go through advanced craft training.

If its appreciated, if their working hard or doing that wee bit extra, more likely to do it than if it's taken for granted. Done it and got no thanks for it, in here it is recognized.

Terms of employment

They do not use agency workers. All are on pretty much the same contracts, same terms, lunch breaks, hours of work, finish at 3.30 on a Friday get a bit of home time. Site 8-4.30. office 8.30-5.00.

They employ by the book, they have an induction checklist, an official offer, their contract, all in writing and detailed as possible, no confusion about what they have signed up for

Wellbeing

They are quite a sympathetic company. When someone lost a good friend, even though they didn't qualify for any time off though they said 'don't come into work';

and that means a lot to people. They are supportive that way; another employee lost her gran in Lithuania, the owner said 'go, it's your gran'. So, there are family moral values which are high and respected. A new staff member was just about to start, sent a mail on the Monday night; my partners mother just died and I a need a day off. There's no timing in these things, they can be helped.

Support

The company just introduced a whole new HR system and that took quite a bit of my time, its private and confidential information so no one could help me, Staff can access things online, training records, holiday requests, makes them feel part of the unit if they are out on site, send out communications.

Control/Voice

They have event like the values alignment meetings for everyone, though it's hard to have everyone at a single meeting, site managers or supervisors do attend when they can, but they can't take everyone off site more than once a year. They Let them know and keep them up to date

Work and Employment

The company has 46 employees. Some staff, joiners, labourers, site managers, contract managers. Others are office based, contracts managers in and out, document controller, HR and office manager, directors, quantity surveyors. Quantity surveying, tradespeople and office.

The owner is Stephen, who was a QS and worked for other companies started the company in 2002 as Worksmart interiors. branched out himself. They have grown

steadily, not dramatically, then in 2012 Worksmart contracts established.

Culture

Their values were established when all in the company got together, they had a big alignment meeting, not only from directors or board members but all also apprentices, collectively decided what was important to each and every one of them.

The big thing, the huge thing they conclude, is teamwork and they know people bang on about and it's a cliché thing but it's absolutely true. It's not easy and difficult to pull people together as a team everyone has different opinions.

It can possibly be a 'con' rather than a 'pro' that everyone does know each other pretty well, more personally than you would do in a bigger organization, so maybe be a wee bit.

Business and Management Development

The local labour market is definitely challenging at times, really trouble trying to get QSs, 2 adverts on the website for a while for a QS and estimator. A trainee attends university getting his degree, growing their own, and grow their own joiners, qualified tradesman targeted to this industry, put through 4 qualified joiners, a further 6-8 on just now. 2 have since left to join another company. It's easy for joiners to get work, so they don't feel tied.

Their issue is the location of work, sometimes it all based in Edinburgh, or Ayrshire or Aberdeen. They go where the work is, they don't have a choice in that. There was a lot in Edinburgh with Ayrshire

based going there and now the reverse with the Edinburgh folk coming to Glasgow and Ayrshire.

Values is a question for their company meeting tomorrow, there is not a lot of people who know them. You don't have to know the exact words as long as you know the focus. They are plastered on the wall, in the staff rest area, in their mind these don't apply to anybody else apart from them not one of those corporate things to impress everyone that walks through the door.

Not everybody gets 100% on customer satisfaction

Personal

The interviewee has been in the company for 4 years from February when there were 8 staff. The last 3 years from that to 46. Dramatic growth. When they started, they were a senior office manager, but HR become more and more part of their role (70%), but they did do HR in other companies, so it is not all new.

They have been in this industry for 25 years, and throughout that time it's just been that they've got a bigger background of the whole thing in this industry. They have been a project manager, out on site, been behind a desk, have seen the whole picture. That naturally progressed to the office manager, they also do PPQs and help in other areas. If in doubt phone them, they have a broad background.

They have worked in different environments, and there is nothing worse than 'them and us'. What Worksmart have is their values and what they instil around those. They won't accept anybody treating anybody badly. It's important.

Conclusions

As an award-winning business Worksmart appreciates people. There has been growth, but the aim is to still be a family run company, a family focused company, a Worksmart family.

Managers appreciate that 'you are never going to please everyone' but would not expect anyone to say that even although there might be instances that things are not 100% for them that it's not fair. That is entirely borne out and seen in the result of the 7 respondents to the survey. The decent work ratings are among the highest in the study in a whole, in most respects.

However, the overall employee evaluation for Worksmart, which they would expect to be higher than the average given the component factor scores, is below the average.

The idea of fulfilment is going to be different for different people and the recruitment and retention issues vary also. Challenges are evident in resourcing some skilled and professional staff, and to retain joiners.

M and M Theatre; Executive Summary and Actions

With an overall rating is 4.2., close to the mean of the study, M and M is evidently a decent work employer. However, the scores on the 6 factors are among the lowest of all the study companies. With measures on concerns also among the highest with recognition and control. This may reflect the nature of the workforce, and the young and creative people employed.

The distinctive nature of the workforce profile, and also the logistical reality of the operations being managed, present distinctive employment challenges, which are resolved both in the everyday and strategically with and substantial degree of care and effort on the part of many people.

In comparison with other cases there was more discussion around aspects of the organizations culture and less discussion around the theme of employee 'control/voice'. This is interesting, given that the single thing that might be worth reflecting on most from the survey data is the suggestion that a concern exists with 'control' about how people work. This concern with control may be intrinsic to the kind of operation being managed, or perhaps there is something to explore further.

They all speak 'panto language', and that is odd and unique.

Actions

1. There are factors other than the 6 they measured which create work quality in this company and industry- these additional factors could be explored to extend the things measured which help identify what matters most and who can make a difference in work quality.
2. Concern exists with 'control' about how people work, this is something to explore further.
3. Include in strategic developments discussion of decent work factors, including the 6 covered here and any additional factors that emerge from reflecting on this report.

M and M Organization Data

Table 1 and 2 show the main findings comparing the study data with M and M. While the overall rating is 4.2., close to the mean of the study, the scores on the 6 factors in table 1 are among the lowest of all the study companies. And the rating on concerns seen in Table 2 (3 =high concern, 1= no concern) are also among the higher on recognition and control. This seems to be showing that the overall experience is definitely decent, though the decent work study factors are not capturing all the factors that matter here. This may reflect the nature of the workforce, and the young and creative people employed.

Table 1 Variables of Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		
	All Participants	Your Organization
Overall employee evaluation of M and M	4.3	3.9
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	3.9
Terms of employment	4.1	3.7
Wellbeing	4.0	3.2
Support	4.0	3.5
Control	3.9	3.1
Pay	3.8	3.5

Concerns	All Participants	Your Organization
Recognition	1.5	1.9
Career	1.4	1.4
Training	1.3	1.1
Control	1.3	1.8
Security	1.2	1.2

M and M Theatre; Significant themes

They started 22 years ago with 14 productions in Ayrshire schools. Now they do 6,500 all over the UK, 35 different productions, 44 schools a day. They are looking at Chinese market.

They promote reading for enjoyment and literacy and provide educational and teacher resource packs linked to the curriculum, in PHSE and History too.

They genuinely believe in live theatre, the magic of theatre. They make theatre affordable and accessible for a new generation. They keep bringing

productions out that the schools want to see. For copyright reasons they do classics that they can reproduce and adapt

They were seen as a panto company an entertainment company now very much seen as an educational company. There are lots of campaigns for reading and literacy. Teachers need and have support, ongoing work preceding and following, so it's an educational exercise for the whole year.

Work and Employment

For the actors it's hard, physical work, away from home, 5 days a week. There is an office team for sales, admin and accounts. They can trade all year round except for 5 weeks. Taking into account school holidays. Scotland, England, Ireland.

Pay

Pay at least minimum wage plus, with incentives for salary staff, the sales team have commission but others too all have an effect on it. The costumes and vans equally matter. Everyone has a vested interest, so a pot for everyone to get commission. Teams on road are included.

2- or 3-times year they book and pay to go Butlins 80s weekend, all paid for. Tour managers went to Majorca on holiday. There is an annual ball in the Hilton at Blackpool. When teams are in Ayrshire, they take them out dinner, or bowling, or the escape room. Lots of social events, as creative people are a slightly different breed. They need the applause and M and M need to retain them, keep them happy and looked after and healthy.

Satisfaction

It's not Hollywood or 'Eastenders'. It's really hard work. Performers have got to start at 8.00, to be in schools early to start and set up. M and M are very honest. It is what it is. Long hours. Hours driving long distances, to set up take down drive, then do the same again, it's a long day. They need to be honest; they do not want them to be there for two weeks then disappearing.

There is intrinsic fulfilment and a broader purpose giving a sense of achievement. Every job can have an element of the mundane, but also everyone is involved in something else. So, everyone can be a duty manager, all staff get to see rehearsals, they all go out together, so they know each other. The office is no ivory tower, and the office staff don't lose sight of that.

Terms of employment

The nature of the work narrows down who they can recruit, as there are rising costs of insurance for drivers under 21, so they can't have that. The workforce has a lot of 18–21-year-olds, lots of actors but these can't be drivers. Telesales is not everyone's cup of tea; they are waged and on commission. They tackle this in different ways, staggered start times between 8-6. That helps working parents, in term times and during schoolworking hours.

If people like the job they can have a job for life, a career path which does not exist in many parts of the entertainment business. They have a 'real job', more or less 9 to 5, that they can love and be passionate about it.

M and M invest so much training in them, and they come on so much in the two weeks, then go out and also be a sound engineer, light engineer, do vocal and dance coaching. They have learnt more with them than in 3 years in a degree. It's like an apprenticeship.

Wellbeing

M and M need to keep all happy and looked after and healthy. Illness is a high impact problem in a team of 4 playing 14 parts with no understudy. Wellbeing is a big thing. Eating disorders, stress. Young people and actors and creative people are usually aware they can have mental health issues with stress; the hunger and need for always being applauded. That can take its toll. For many it is the first time away from home, at age 18 and in 'big brother house' mode, living with others and arguing and falling out. That's stressful, to fall out but still share a home with them. They can be isolated, so they do things to get them to mix. every month M and M have a 1 to 1 with a company manager, almost like a mother. Eating disorders are an issue, so they keep an eye on it.

With 24-7 and living together, there is a duty manager and confidential support line available. There might be problem with tour manager, and they don't want people running away in the middle of the night or they lose business. They have more than a statutory a duty of care with young people inexperienced in life.

Support

They had liP for many years but did not renew it was very expensive for little value. A good school's provider kitemark, or something for schools they are approved by would be good.

Control/Voice

Not covered in discussions

Context

There are 20 in the office team; these do the sales team, phone all schools, accounts and admin. There are 22 touring teams, so they need 22 lots of accommodation and 22 vans, a vehicle manager, set department and wardrobe dept and writing department. They audition all over UK.

Production is not local, they come from show directors and actors all over the world. Worked for them as an actor, come up through the ranks, career progression, take on an actor team of 4 has a tour leader for the cast. Then can become a tour manager and get into direction and put together new shows. Many started as newbies with them and worked their way up.

The workforce is over 100 at peak times. The directors are two, one was a primary school teacher, and one was theatre director. The standard of theatre in schools was seen to be poor; they thought they can do it better, so they pooled talent and resources

Culture

Teams are young. Age is 18 minimum, and most parts in pantos lend themselves to children/young people. It's a young person's game (not being age discriminatory). They are a bit like holiday reps, who at the end of education think "I am good at singing and dancing, but can't

afford to go to drama school, and/or not enough talent for the 'glamour roles'."

They get to travel, accommodation paid, transport paid, and get disposable income. They can do that and use it for a few years get a deposit on a house and then a 'real job', or train as teachers. They get a flair for working with children and they have good career progression here.

M and M are members of literacy trust, anti-bullying, road safety, good PR and tag on to campaigns. It is good to be on their wavelength and get their feedback. they feel an obligation to follow up causes as they make their living out of it. M and M do a lot in terms of CSR but do not 'put it out there'. Charity productions, visiting hospices, they do it just as its nice.

They are genuinely proud, not just selling a script, they really all believe in it. Everyone is asked to contribute to campaigns and social media. Everybody gets involved in everything. To get inter-department respect and get rid of the 'I work harder than them', the office staff will go out and help. Actors come in to see what it's like for sales. So, camaraderie matters.

It's a gamble but they interview as well, when the norm just auditions. But only let one person misbehave and their reputation is done, so performers are role models and ambassadors, it's a big remit to fill. They work so hard and do so well they can party too.

Business and Management Development

They do everything in house. Decide what to perform. Make sets, make and design

costumes, recruit, rehearse. 44 invoices, book again. It is “a big old mouth to feed”, touring teams have 4 people in them. At capacity they have 88 people plus floating cover for vans custom built to fit sets in. A heck of a thing to run and manage. £3.5 Million turnover, and costs are high, with fuel, accommodation, and behind the scenes costs.

Panto season was the core time, but now this is extended from September-February, such is the demand. After 3-4 years needed to retain staff and sustain it all year round. While being very niche what they do, a specific art form can't get someone from a temping agency. They now have classic literature adaptations, then they can keep staff and have them salaried all year. They are so niche they have to look after their staff, most come from far afield and they are specialists in what they do.

They have to have their eye on the ball, as new things come through all the time; for example, PHSE curriculum for life, and things come out and it varies. In Birmingham it might be gritty things, like knife crime, violence, human trafficking. Or in Ayrshire, respect and friendship. They market and target for different areas. The Classic book, Oliver Twist can be read for enjoyment, or about austerity, or grooming, or child bereavement, to tailor to whatever pushes the buttons. PTAs are struggling now; they ask parents for a contribution but cannot exclude those who don't contribute. All used to, but few do now.

It is very hard to get schools to part with the cash, budgets are tight. Theatre was lovely and was a treat, but they cannot afford treats for the children anymore. They need to quantify what is in it, be viable and satisfying. For LAs and what

they want to be attacking. Different authorities, some with academy status schools in England who manage own budget. Or a catholic secondary that has a budget for feeder primaries, Scotland is LAs, private schools, church, School managers, Business manager. Sometimes the PTA. Head teacher says 'I would like it but need to speak to my business manager, each place is unique. Invoicing is a nightmare!

They go in and do a whole production; a whole set, pyrotechnics and all. Saves them the costs of the trip out and the logistics of that, they are selling convenience and low cost (transport) and insurance. Special needs issues make it hard to take groups of children out of the building. Learning difficulties children can participate in their own environment and are so not excluded.

Personal

The manager interviewed said of her experience; “It's a huge task, and when you do it every day you don't think about it. I did it every day as general manager for 20 years, then I stepped aside for strategy development, and when I took a step back I though blimey how did I juggle all that and with my phone going 24-7. Sometimes you don't realize what you do”.

Conclusion

M and M is evidently a decent work employer. However, the scores on the 6 factors are among the lowest of all the study companies. With results on concerns also among the highest regarding recognition and control. This may reflect the nature of the workforce,

and the young and creative people employed.

KCP Waste Management; Executive Summary and Actions

This organization represents a case where consistent and extensive success as a decent work employer is evident. The reasons for this are developed and discussed based on the interview with the owner, and with reference to the decent work facts and other themes that emerge from the interview analysis.

The organization fulfils the expectations of a decent work employer in the eyes of the employees. No single factor stands out as being the reason for this, there is achievement across all 6 factors. Consequently, there are no specific concerns highlighted where there are gaps between employee expectations and work experiences. The management of the organization appreciate that decent work is a goal which is meaningful both personally and for business success and growth. The culture which has been established around values, is an expression of this. This is especially relevant as the work of the operators is difficult and messy, and paperwork associated with that for them which is challenging.

The challenges of growth are not about becoming a more decent employer; they are more to do with the challenges of the local labour market for the retention of operators and professional staff who might help with that growth. They are also. To do with addressing issues about pay other than basic pay levels, and mindset to support growth integrated with ay and rewards.

It is clear that the personal experience, insights and commitments of the managers are the underlying sources of being a decent work employer. Sustaining and building on those can be a challenge if growth involves those managers adopting more 'hands off' roles and bringing in more professional and other support kinds of staff. The appropriate actions here are.

1. Share results with staff and celebrate achievements
2. Consider what decent work variables look like for a growth-oriented future (already doing this with pay)
3. Plan for sustaining decent work values as the two owner/director roles evolve with business and personal circumstances

Organization Data

10 people completed the survey. This is a very high response rate from a small organization. The high participation rate, given the results below, is an indication of a very healthy working environment and team.

Table1. Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		
	All Participant s	Your Organizatio n
Overall employee evaluation of KCP	4.3	4.1
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	4.5
Terms of employment	4.1	4.5
Wellbeing	4.0	4.4

Support	4.0	4.3
Control	3.9	4.3
Pay	3.8	4.4

Table 1 shows that on all the 6 factors KCP rated more consistently highly than in other cases in this study. At the same time the overall rating is slightly lower than for other cases in the study.

Concerns	All Participants	Your Organization
Recognition	1.5	1.0
Career	1.4	1.2
Training	1.3	1.0
Control	1.3	1.1
Security	1.2	1.0

Table 2 shows that your organization employees have lower concern than those in other cases in the study (3 =high concern, 1= no concern). This is consistent with the data in Table 1.

Significant themes

1. KCP are more than a 'tanker cleaning company'. Their USP is to problem solve, to be invaluable for doing that, which costs more than just the services of a tanker company. They will go clean the tanker but also investigate and problem solve.
2. From the point of view of growth, it costs more to be a decent employer, but it is sustainable and still makes good margins. Investing to improve the building, kit and training rather than personal wealth.
3. "It's all very nice and we love each other but we need wealth creation on the next stage of the journey".
4. One director says "I see the good in things, my mum said to me when I

was 15 you need to take your rose-coloured glasses off, I spent most of my life trying to take them off and then I got to last year and I was I kind of like life through my rose-coloured glasses. You've just got to work a bit harder at it and spread it about a bit to realise your vision. I feel their loyalty."

5. The view of decent work is that as a developed country they have to make the business model work, though some companies don't do that.

Work and Employment

Operators need to be physically fit, using heavy equipment, outside in all weathers, dealing with smelly stuff. Lots of things make the work difficult. Operators are unskilled, don't need experience, can work away on Monday back Friday, all over the UK, with smelly waste.

The local labour market is a challenge, as it is very difficult to recruit operators. For specialists, professionals to support growth and business development, it is also tough. For office personnel less so.

Pay

The Living Wage is paid, and the company is business pledge branded.

They are not performance bonus oriented but growth oriented. They are not materialistic, so when aiming for wealth creation they seem to want the wealth for someone else; working for someone else or working for each other. These are the foundations for a high-performance team.

Satisfaction

Office satisfaction is easier. Waste is smelly, operators work in protection gear high hazard and low skill, shovelling waste.

How they recruit to get someone like a graduate out of university to come and help develop the business is a challenge. Money is not an issue, but they can't offer the same kind of job satisfaction.

Terms of employment

No zero hours contract, sometimes they have fits and bursts when they have other companies with operational personnel they can ask 'do you have a spare person' when they are a person down'. Preferred working hours in the office but can't be flexible on site.

Wellbeing

Operator doing high hazard work. A lot of what they do with external training is work but is also teaching things that might help in personal life.

Support

People come in with no idea what their business is and they learn it.

Control/Voice

They problem solve, sometimes starting with no clear objective. Staff go and investigate and make proposals, contextualization for the client. They encourage staff to turn moans into implementable change.

Confidence and mannerisms when out on site, and meeting with 'suits' and 'keyboard' based contacts is important; to feel able to challenge them. Tell them 'No'.

Context

The company has 2 directors, 11 employees. 5 in the office, one part-time, 1 work experience looking at IT support. Financial controller is more ad hoc. Currently 5 Operators.

The owners are a husband-and-wife team. There can be challenges if both are off at the same time, which impacts their work-life balance.

Culture

One director went to university and qualified as a chartered engineer. They see skills in other people, but literacy and numeracy can let them down, and that annoys them. They empower staff to feel good, doing menial but high risk and high hazard work. What is missing was that the staff are all good individually, but they need to better visualize their culture.

They were saying be open, but not everyone was feeling it. There is the small family business syndrome; 'you can't comment on X or it gets back to them'.

They made the acronym CHES; Communication, Honesty, Efficiency, Service, Safety. CHES helps them focus on 'where are we going wrong?'. There are the two things everyone brings, the values they bring, Communication and honesty. Then they train to get efficiency, safety and service.

One director did growth advantage programme at a University for 10 months. They got business tools, and they can give them to other people.

Business and Management Development

They know for succession it's not a civil engineer they need, it's a chemical engineer. Wastewater treatment, dirty water, environmental protection, the whole focus has been about that, and improving conditions on site. The directors can take a higher-level strategic role if the other roles that take a lot of time can be covered.

They have been short staffed for a while. Some start and stick it out for a few weeks but not longer. They are almost constantly recruiting. Three staff here for five plus years everyone else for a few months, usually due to family changes.

They don't allow the client to tell them what the problem is, they diagnose and solve problems. Their USP is to be invaluable, so that costs more than a tanker company.

There is a lot one director does as a qualified engineer. They took on an R&D student, a local person, to provide her with something interesting to do and for pay before she went on to a corporate career.

Conclusion

This organization represents a case where consistent and extensive success as a decent work employer is evident. The reasons for this are developed and discussed based on the interview with the owner, and with reference to the decent work facts and other themes that emerge from the interview analysis.

Thorne Travel: Executive Summary and Actions

Thorne Travel scores above average and the highest on all decent work factors, with least concerns expressed.

This is a testament to the company, consistent with the acclaim it receives from other sources. The company is a real champion of decent work for a number of reasons.

- The clear, central and essential commitments of the director to care and concern for all employees
- The provision across all factors of high standards
- The efforts made to ensure fit with the ethos and customer needs of the business
- The innovation, some planned and some emergent, which has been seen in the past and continues presently, reflecting a dynamic and team spirit throughout the company
- A culture that flows from the personal focus of the director on knowing and meeting their own work-life needs and expecting to fulfil the same for others.

Action points

1. The challenge is to sustain the high standards achieved, as and when the circumstances creating these changes; the key one is self-evidently any succession plan for the director as and when that becomes an issue, or other key staff as and when they may exit the company.
2. Sharing knowledge and experience of being able to attain such high standards would be of value to the business community in Scotland, as well as locally.

Organization Data

Tables 1 and 2 show the main data from the study, comparing all participants with your organization. There was a good response from Thorne Travel, with 11 completing the survey. Thorne Travel scores above average and the highest on all factors, with least concerns expressed.

Variables of Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		
	All P	Your Organization
Overall employee evaluation of you as a decent work employer	4.3	5.0
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	4.9
Terms of employment	4.1	4.9
Wellbeing	4.0	5.0
Support	4.0	4.9
Control	3.9	4.9
Pay	3.8	4.8

Concerns (3 =high concern, 1= no concern)	All	Your Organization
Recognition	1.5	1.1
Career	1.4	1.1
Training	1.3	1.1
Control	1.3	1.0
Security	1.2	1.0

Significant Themes

They have this year won a national award as UK best travel agency, and No1 in Scotland.

They aim for empowerment and staff to make decisions, people don't have to ask the Director, they are in total control

But they don't follow the norm, they don't look at other travel agents, they look at different areas of the world and get ideas from there

A new part of the business Thorne Travel Heritage, going out to countries to get people to come visit Scotland, and doing VR for that.

There are clear, central and essential commitments from the director with care and concern for all employees.

Work and Employment

Pay

Accredited on living wage and business pledge.

Satisfaction

This year, 2019, was their biggest by far for awards; with great customer feedback, mystery shopping visits, suppliers' feedback, and meeting ethical and responsible targets.

They aim for empowerment and staff to make decisions, people don't have to ask me, they are in total control, they have the skills and tools, and a target to hit, goal to achieve. They mix it up a bit, sell different products. One staff member is up for travel agent of the year, a fun-loving festival and 'Ibetta' girl whose boundaries have been pushed. They sent her to the over 40s cruise up the Norwegian Fjords, to see things she'd never seen and came back saying she had loved it. That's rewarding.

Terms of employment

Flexible working for the staff with kids, so once the kids are in bed they can log on at night and work from home. Everyone they employ is local. They can do homework, but for the type of people here they feel better, with other people to bounce ideas off of. For other travel agents, such as Jet2 or Thomas Cook homework can be OK, but not here.

Wellbeing

Wellbeing is managed by the Director, and HR brought in in as a contract. They provide private medical care, access to online and physical, and phone up, and an occupational therapist.

Support

After a few challenges they do all their own basic training. They bring people in and train them, in the qualities they want to be customer facing, to think on their feet, and not be afraid of change. They

don't have to have travelled; they can teach them that. They have a person who heads up the customer journey manager, with a number of courses on the go. Another from Barrhead (another travel agent), with lots of experience, who is finding working here a big difference from her previous job.

In other companies they may have great knowledge but be struggling to speak with customers. Here they need to be used to people as they sell all over the world Australia, America, Sweden, and they expect a different kind of conversation than 'here is 7 nights in Tenerife'. They need to strip it back and, painful as it is, take a month to recruit, that is less painful than having someone not right for the business, not done anything wrong, but not fitting with what they need.

Control/Voice

They have a rigorous interview process, and don't ask for a cv. They ask people to sell themselves and why they want to work for Thorne, instantly people get freaked as it's not the norm. But they don't follow the norm, they don't look at other travel agents, they look at different areas of the world and get ideas from there, other companies in other parts of the world. This means they get the right people but spend a lot of money on that and on training, a huge amount.

They don't do formal appraisal, one to ones. They don't want to wait till end of month, if the Director is not happy, they have a conversation, if they are happy, they have a conversation. Once a year there is a conversation on pay and where are you going. This is better than a formal structure. They have flipchart through the back, with ideas written on there, a host of ideas come out. At the start of work,

they look at the flip chart. They also have a Facebook, private chat group, so if you walk past a shop and see something, take a picture and post it, if I'm in hotel, take a picture and share.

Context

They are open 7 days a week, and only close 3 days a year. Peak season is January, used to be heavy peak, it still is huge chunk of business in January. Then September is the quietest period.

It was challenging in the beginning, in a traditional industry and people came with a traditional view. For example, Thomas Cook- trained on their products and they are sold a Thomas Cook product. If you can't do that then there was a pecking order of others, not always the best. Not really giving customer choice. Thorne have brought staff in from Thomas Cook, and who used to work for TUI, with the view 'why would you sell the competition?' In here it is what is right for the customer, not being told what to sell but dealing with specifics of each customer e.g., flights and time. For some this is totally alien and they can't do it.

A new part of the business Thorne Travel Heritage, going out to countries to get people to come visit Scotland, and doing Virtual reality (VR) for that. No one else does that. They are only one that offers coach trips. Tour operators do it, not travel agents.

Tour operators are aimed at a particular type of tour, they do 'cauliflower head' tours with loads of people sitting on buses. Others like Rabbie tours, they appeal to small bus groups and people with rucksacks, who have pay for everything additionally when they get to

tour stops. Thorne are aiming to be more bespoke; say for three days in Loch Lomond. Choose from a Lodge stay, highland dancing, canoeing, going over to Arran and an outdoor centre, travel by sea plane, something a bit different, something quirkier. Perhaps farmhouse dining with fresh meat sourced from right outside. So not a trail-finder in a hostel or sit on a coach for 8 hours, do lots and get to choose. The start and finish and hotels are there, but they can also be quirky; provide robes and noodles in rooms for Chinese, or beer for Australians. Staff go with Thorne's own packs to hotels, something slightly different, to dress that room to suit the customer

Currently they have 19 people. They don't increase numbers they, increase hours. 4 staff work 20 hours and can jump up to full time. They have 8 casual people who do experience work and can go out on trips who are first aid trained, a face to have the business on the coaches.

9 years ago, the Director decided to do something for herself, having enjoyed travelling and being a planner and organizer. She had worked in travel and banking. The vision was just Her and a couple of girls in a small business and that would be it, to take her into retirement.

Culture

They did a marketing video a few years back that became widely circulated and even went viral; a fun parody on the Virgin Air hostess models fronted advertisement of the time. Where the models do a funky walk, that does not equate to reality, it's a fantasy world. The video was made for their local PR night, then put out to customers who could not make that and got taken up by Radio 1 and others. Some thought the video was a

genuine but risible advertisement, for including the real Thorne staff who appeared in it as they were "too fat!" But these were just normal size 16 women, quite typical. The ad went viral, but that was not meant; it got 1.5 million hits in 2 days. The publicity was great. It was shown worldwide, Australia, S Africa, and opened up to whole new audience. They grew from 6 to 14 staff in the few months after this.

Business and Management Development

When they started out, they would always provide quality, it was not about pile high and sell cheap. If I wouldn't stay in a place it wouldn't sell it, as simple as that. Hit badly and hard in the early years. The Euro, a big airline went bust, the ash cloud incident happened, a Turkish airline went bust too. They quickly had to look at cash flow, as they are not paid till customers travel, they approached a coach company, set up Thorne Experience, which brings in now same amount as Thorne Travel, 5M turnover 50% each.

They started across the road in a small shop but have grown dramatically. They did not know what to do where to go, then saw that this shop had lain empty tough it was a wreck. They could not buy it but got it rented and did all the work to make it theirs from an empty shell. They did that.

They had outgrown their first premises; the Director had to think 'do I employ homeworkers or open another shop?'. A big discussion as they didn't want to have more shops they had to travel to, the whole reason for starting her own company was not travel but to be here,

and if they had places all over that would dilute it.

They have a project manager, a lawyer, travel consultants at different level from some new to some with 40 years' experience, social media graduates and apprentices, admin, business to business, experience manager comes up with ideas, quite a variety of roles. 2.7 Million through social media. It's massive for them.

When moving premises some said 'good god woman that are you doing' but the director had a plan. They have customer nights for free food and drink and have a party, do an Oscars night to thank people and other businesses.

Innovations emerge. For example, the director was in Singapore, went into a bar, fell in love with how they had done it, set up their room, a bar with a sliding door that allowed them to do different things when they were not busy, it was done it in style. That was the inspiration for their Topsy tea events, using old fashioned teapots and cups but for cocktails. And that brought in an employee from the Seamill Hydro hotel, as the director had seen and loved the way he interacted with customers; he is now also a sales assistant, having never worked in travel. So, think about something different, quirkier.

Personal

The Director was born locally and has travelled the world, but home is still here, her family is still here. Her family grew up here, they moved back here had their kids brought up here, and still travel the world. They wanted to be close to home, fed up travelling, get out of the house and walk to work walk, see the grandkids,

When she got caught up in the PR experience around the viral video, she was offered deals to be followed around; a fast buck would have felt wrong, not right for her, or for the business. She is not a celebrity; she is a mum and a gran who wants to put her feet up and slippers on.

Conclusion

Thorne Travel scores above average and the highest on all decent work factors, with least concerns expressed.

This is a testament to the company, consistent with the acclaim it receives from other sources. The company is a real champion of decent work for a number of reasons.

brodie
ENGINEERING

1. Sustaining decent work standards through and beyond a strategic review, with respect to the total picture which might include different labour market contexts
2. Reflecting on what the issue of 'recognition' means and options for improving that.
3. Making the most of HR knowledge and expertise as a business partner

Executive Summary and Actions

Brodie Engineering is a leading rail rolling stock engineering business. It has grown in recent years, and now there is an ongoing strategy review, for the business and premises and infrastructure, with significant change expected soon.

Managers in Brodie believed they were a decent employer in the area, and the data provided here reinforces that view. The money matters, but it's still other things that make a difference in the SME. Terms of employment are the highest rated decent work factor here and pay the lowest. The extent of concerns reported are similar to the study mean for all good decent work employers, with security and control the least concerning and recognition the most concerning.

Part of the situation is changing leadership, with an HR manager influence becoming more integrated with that; that is progressing but slowly, take the long view and it's not all going to get done tomorrow. Selling HR to the MD of the company or the influencers is a process over time, which can be tough.

Actions

Organization Data

Table 1 and Table 2 show the responses from all and the 24 Brodie people who completed the survey. This shows that Brodie is close to the mean on most variables, with terms of employment highest and pay lowest.

	All	Brodie
Overall evaluation of Brodie	4.3	4.1
6 factors of decent work		
Satisfaction	4.1	3.9
Terms of employment	4.1	4.0
Wellbeing	4.0	3.8
Support	4.0	3.8
Control	3.9	3.9
Pay	3.8	3.6
Table 1 Decent Work (5 = max best score possible, 1= minimum)		

Table 2 shows that the extent of concerns reported (1=no concern to 3= high concern) are similar to the study mean, with security and control the least concerning and recognition the most concerning

	All	Brodie
Recognition	1.5	1.8
Career	1.4	1.6
Training	1.3	1.5

Control	1.3	1.3
Security	1.2	1.3
Table 2 Concerns about work and employment		

This shows that Brodie Engineering is indeed a decent work employer. Managers in Brodies believed they were a decent employer in the area, open to getting ideas.

Brodie Significant themes

The company is a leading rolling stock engineering business. It has grown in recent years, and now there is an ongoing strategy review, for the business and premises and infrastructure, with significant change expected soon. They are as big as they can be where they are. If they expand do, they have people in those locations, or do they go into consultancy with very good engineers?

The money matters of course, and in Brodie Engineering pay is thought to be very good, but it's still little things that make a difference in the SME. For professional jobs there are quite rich pickings, but trades are hard to recruit.

Brodie Engineering can design and manufacture, a fully working workshop, with fitters, electricians' welders' pipe-builders' painters, every skilled trade you can think of, and need to utilize those skills. Tradespeople, electricians and coach builders are at a premium

Part of the situation is changing leadership; it's progressing but slowly, take the long view and it's not all going to get done tomorrow. Selling HR to the MD of the company or the influencers is tough

Work and Employment

It's not a dirty job but it's a hands-on job, and there is a huge skills gap. In the 90s the sector stopped apprenticeships, so lots of people at end of the career and at the beginning but not many in the middle. Brodie Engineering have recently started five new apprentices aged 18-19.

The labour market is very competitive. The biggest competitor is across the line from them. They do similar types of work, bid against each other, railyards in Glasgow. Brodie Engineering have 17 apprentices, started that, some new and some upskilling. Grow their own and the retention good enough not to seek it externally.

Skilled workers may go for 50 pence an hour that's the railway industry, there is very little loyalty.

When they advertise for engineers, they attracted a lot from oil and gas. It was surprising the amount of people from Ayrshire applying, people had chased the money in Aberdeen and offshore, now that has collapsed, they are back in their hometown. For professional jobs there are quite rich pickings, but for trades it can be hard to recruit.

Average workforce age is about 44, with tenure about 2.3 years, though some 14-15 years and some just brought in. In gender, it's predominantly male. There are 8 females, and they do have a female engineering manager, that's a key job here. She had kids and lived in Kilmarnock so it attracted her to be here. They are a local employer that pays quite well, not a huge range of benefits but it's a very nice environment.

Pay

Variations in pay due to a workforce with employed, labour supplied by others, and agency contract staff. This causes problems as people talk, 'I am on 22 pounds an hour'. Brodie Engineering have to have that open communication and explain you get holidays, sick pay, pensions, then you are not that far away in a total reward perspective. Have to educate their employees to retain that the grass not always greener.

Brodies pay people well, employment is long term, no temporary contracts. But there is a real shortage at the price Brodies can afford. In terms of resourcing, there has been a change with more and more skilled trades going as contractors. They form their own limited companies, pay rates very high £22 an hour.

Satisfaction

Tradespeople like what they do, but every job has its boring and mundane bits, though if there is too much of that it breeds discontent. If Brodie Engineering have a crash damaged train that has to be stripped out and cleaned, that is unpopular work. In the office context there are no clear lines of demarcation between jobs, everyone does a bit of everything. Brodie Engineering have job description, but HR cannot issue them, as the MD is concerned that if they see them, they will 'stick' to them.

Engineers have a traditional pride. Brand new trains being built is for them an opportunity and a threat; as Brodie Engineering can win the fitting out of them so that is new work, but it is a threat as 70 percent of their business is repair and maintaining the old. These should be in service for 25 years but been used for 30-49 years, with corrosion issues. A big

part of their transformation was the Edinburgh-Glasgow trains contract to upgrade the train, which staff still talk about that yet; with trainsets in and turned out in 3 weeks, no snagging, the quality was great. And if finished by the Thursday they got Friday off.

A lot of people want to work in Glasgow, as Ayrshire is quite rural. Then again people have tried it and didn't like it and now want to stay local.

Terms of employment

Brodie Engineering don't treat contractors employed through an agency any differently, they can use the facilities, follow same rules, and time, they treat them equally.

All staff have exactly same terms and conditions, though different hours. The workshop is 40 hours a week, 7.30-and half day on a Friday. The office are 37 hours a week, with flexitime 9.30-3.30.

Wellbeing

Brodie Engineering have a H&S manager, safety critical stuff in the railways. They aim for an open culture and no threat.

In the local communities, in Kilmarnock especially, there are a lot of financial issues and mental health issues, social problems. Brodie Engineering try to help people on an individual basis, with problems in the family, and financial issues. They can offer employee loans or advice, but they can only help people so far. Some can take the micky; they are not here any longer. That's the kind of culture.

Brodie Engineering have an occupational health provider, and do annual medical checks, as have to have benchmark checks

on audio, eyesight and skin, and they add on BMI and cholesterol, a talk to the nurse, maybe refer on. They detected an issue with high blood pressure for example. They refused to put in vending machines with rubbish food, instead offering a fruit drop into the canteen. When it was threatened to stop this as fruit was being dumped in the bin, staff wanted it to be kept going

Support

They looked at Westfield health, not quite private health service, but staff can get access. They canvassed views and they said, 'how much does that cost?' The figure was about £500 a year, and some staff said, 'well just give us the money'! Benefits like these are not perceived to be benefits by blue collar, though office staff would really appreciate them. There was opposition to starting a pension, but HR had to say, 'you have no choice', instead spend a lot of time with the pension provider and they were good explaining it in simple terms; before, without knowledge, if just told in straight terms they would reject it out of hand.

Control/Voice

There are monthly team leader meetings, employee forum, and team leaders asked to get issues from teams, everything from HR stuff, pay rise and health and safety. When this was first introduced, back in the day, HR had to go through the pain about answering stupid questions before they get into constructive conversations and feedback and coming up with suggestions.

Some are 'Philadelphia lawyers', wanting to tell others what they can and cannot do. HR have a relationship with them, they come and have a moan, and things are taken on board. An example of a

changed thing is the refurbished canteens, with some trivial but important things like putting in microwaves.

Context

When the current HR manager started Brodie Engineering had 60 employees, now 93. It was the MD with his wife doing all the manager/secretary things. The Production manager used to manage everything from discipline to welfare to holidays and all other sorts of stuff. Support also sometimes from lawyers, but they are quite expensive.

Culture

The HR manager on appointment had a culture shock, that the MD was not ready for HR to be so strong in the organization and they pushed back on a lot of change. It's been trial and error process for the first year, now its fully accepted, and the HR manager sits on the lead team. But it's taken three years to break down the barriers of trust and respect for the function of HR.

The company set up values. Who are we? what is the Brodie way? For this they did a group session and Brodie values written out then discussed with individual. HR was not the wicked witch or the police, but approachable, which they 'regret' now as the door is never shut!

Business and Management Development

Brodie Engineering had no real HR process, to grow they would have to have HR in the organization. They did the basics, offer letters, paying people, no real

contract in place, the things you would expect.

4 years ago, when the HR manager started, they said a web site was important, the one Brodie Engineering had looked like a throwback, so they took on a business development manager. In the last 12 months they have built the page with career website, profiles of main team and employees, their work, and business development team. This has had a big impact. Recently they 50 applications some advertised and some on spec.

Selling HR to the MD of the company or the influencers is tough, as they can think that HR specialists don't know much about SMEs. To which the HR manager replied, "I don't have to, but I will learn it, but I do know about people and that's what you need". They started having conversations and others have come round to seeing the value, especially the production manager was happier as he had help with basic HR stuff, recruitment, absence, and that also added value. When he started saying HR is good for us the MD also came round.

Personal; The HR Manager Perspective

The HR manager had the strategic background, and experience of how a business works. They believe HR can build their influence over time. If in an SME key people are saying 'We can't afford HR', which is common, then argue to bring in someone from HR who has capability more than just HR admin, like a business partner, perhaps to start for 2-3 days week. Let them set up the processes, show that it works, and build up trust, doing little things that may be basic; like

cutting down sickness absence by bringing in the 'Bradford scale'. This was done at Brodies, and reduced absence from 6% to 1.5 % and even the sceptics thought it was fantastic. People know now that if they are absent, they will be looked at and have a difficult conversation on return. Build that achievement into a cost benefit, an instant benefit.

The HR manager in Brodies is coming to the latter phase of their career, having had in the past been in big companies with the wonderful salary and the bonus, the great pension. They worked hard for that; being on call, it could be relentless. Especially at the end of her last big company job, with significant redundancies to be managed, that was horrible. There are HR people like her, people who want to keep working but take a step back from that level of big company challenge, with experience, and help a smaller company. A friend who worked in another big company also recently took redundancy and is helping out a day a week with a construction company. They started doing a little bit and are now doing 4 days a week.

If you have a business head, it's not just about HR. Many may be predominantly women in their 30s or 40s who have had a family and want to go back to work or do something with more substance. It's interesting in an SME, you are not pigeonholed in a functional role, you have an influence on everything. It's a complete role, not like a large corporate place, doing a specific thing and no one else knows.

Conclusions

The company has grown in recent years, and now there is an ongoing strategy

review. The data provided here reinforces the view that the money matters, but it's still other things that make a difference in the SME. The extent of concerns reported are similar to the study mean for all good decent work employers, with security and control the least concerning and recognition the most concerning. Part of

the situation is changing leadership, with HR manager influence becoming more integrated; that is progressing but slowly.

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